

Multiple Information, Shannon-like Entropy and Thermodynamic Entropy

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The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution is compatible with Shannon's entropy which in turn is equivalent to thermodynamic entropy. In such a case, $\ln(P(e))$ is information which matches the information e (energy) brought by a particle into a collision. In (1) we considered "altered" probabilities $P_{alt}(e) = P(e)/[1+P(e)]$ to describe information associated with a collision of fermions or bosons.

In this note we try to reinterpret $P_{alt}(e)$ for fermions or bosons as two pieces of information which combine to create the information e brought into a collision. In principle there could be more terms. It is noted that these terms are linear in $P(e)$. They lead to a sum of Shannon-like entropies i.e. $P(e)\ln[P(e)] + [1-P(e)]\ln[1-P(e)]$.

We also consider the link with thermodynamic entropy i.e. for fixed parameters: $dE = \sum_i e_i dP(e_i) = T dS$. We argue that "entropy" should also have the form $\sum_i F(P(e_i)) dP(e_i)$. In (2) we showed that one may obtain the form $\ln(P(e_i)) P(e_i)$ from this consideration alone. Here we extend this idea to Shannon-like terms $(a+bP(e_i)) \ln[a+bP(e_i)]$.

First Source of Information

The Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution in an ideal gas may be measured by creating a small hole in the gas wall and analyzing the velocity of the particles emitted. If one has an ensemble of such gasses with N members where N is large, then $P(e)$ is the probability for a particle with energy e to emerge. If N is large, one expects that $NP(e)$ particles with energy e should have emerged during the measuring process (taking one particle from each gas). Writing the overall product probability yields:

$$P(\text{overall}) = \text{Product over } i \text{ } P(e_i)^{NP(e_i)} \quad ((1))$$

Taking \ln of both sides yields $\exp(\sum_i P(e_i) \ln[P(e_i)])$ on the RHS which is linked to Shannon's entropy for a particular piece of information namely $\ln(P(e_i))$. This is identical to a calculation in Information Theory (3).

For an MB gas this is the only information so $P(e_i)$ or $\ln(P(e_i))$ also appears for two body elastic scattering i.e.

$$P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_3)P(e_4) \text{ with } e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((2))$$

Thus one may equate $\ln(P(e_i))$ with $-e_i/T$ (T =parameter=temperature) because $\ln(P(e_i))$ is the only information in the system and must be equal to the physical information e_i .

More Than One Source of Information

We argue that the same logic to ((1)) should apply for an ideal gas of fermions or bosons. Then why aren't such gasses described by the MB distribution? We argued in (2) that ((2)) does

not apply i.e. there is an “alternate” type of independent probability (i.e. it is a function of $P(e_i)$) which describes collisions. Collisions create and maintain equilibrium and so this is the probability or related information to consider. What about $P(e_i)$? This is also linked to information. Thus we argue that there may be more than one type of information in a system. For fermions, $P(e_i)$ gives information about the number of particles with energy e_i which is identical to the probability that a particle with e_i may try to collide, but $1-P(e_i)$ gives a second kind of information about the probability for a collision to produce a particle in the energy state e_i . If a particle already exists in e_i , by the Pauli principle a second one may not scatter into this state. Thus these two pieces of information linked to $P(e_i)$ must be combined in a manner such that they are directly linked to e_i the only overall piece of information brought into a collision. A reaction balance approach gives this relationship:

$$P(e_1) [1-P(e_3)] P(e_2) [1-P(e_3)] = P(e_3)[1-P(e_1)] P(e_4) [1-P(e_2)] \quad ((3))$$

Thus $\ln[P(e_i) / (1-P(e_i))] = A e_i + B$ where $A = 1/T$ and $B = -u/T$ where T is temperature and u the chemical potential.

For the MB case there is only one parameter $1/T$ which is linked to average energy. In the fermion or boson case, one has two parameters, $1/T$ linked to average energy and $-u/T$ linked to average number of particles. Thus for the MB case there is one overall energy e_i which is brought by a particle into a collision, one information $\ln(P(e_i))$ and one parameter $1/T$. For fermions and bosons, there is one e_i , two pieces of information $\ln(P(e_i))$ and $\ln(1+P(e_i))$ and two parameters $1/T$ and $-u/T$.

One may next ask: How does one convert $\ln[P(e_i) / (1-P(e_i))]$ into an entropy? One cannot simply use Shannon’s recipe with $P_{\text{alternate}} = P(e_i) / (1-P(e_i))$. (There are even issues with the normalization of this quantity in terms of a probability summing to 1.)

In (4) Kaniadakis proposes a sum of Shannon-like entropy terms:

$$\text{Sum over } i \quad -P(e_i) \ln[P(e_i)] - (1-P(e_i)) \ln\{ [1-P(e_i)] \} \quad ((4))$$

For a gas of bosons, one may change the minus sign to positive in the above as there is an enhancement probability or source of information of $1+P(e_i)$. In other words the more particles that are in e_i , the greater the probability for another to scatter into this e_i state.

Information Theory Model

Equation ((1)) follows an information theory model. The overall probability given by the Product over i expression should also be equal to $1/N$ the number of possible arrangements. This suggests that each arrangement has the same probability. In the MB case:

$$\ln(\text{number of arrangements}) = \ln\{ N! / (\text{Product over } i \text{ } n_i!) \} \text{ approx } =$$

$$N \ln(N) - \text{Sum over } i \text{ } n_i \ln(n_i) \quad ((5))$$

Thus Shannon's entropy appears in this way as well. For the case of two pieces of information, one may treat them as two independent probabilities and write:

$$\text{Probability overall fermions} = \text{Product over } i \ P(e_i)^{N P(e_i)} (1-P(e_i))^{N(1-P(e_i))} \quad ((6))$$

$\ln(\text{Probability overall fermions})$ should be equal to $-\ln(\text{number of arrangements})$, but in this case ((5)) does not apply. One must use the extra piece of information (namely that two fermions cannot occupy the same state or for bosons, that a level may be occupied by any number of particles). This leads to a different calculation of the number of arrangements. From (5):

Fermions arrangements = $g_i ! / [n_i ! (g_i - n_i)!]$ ((7)) where g_i is the number of subcells i the i th cell. There may be 0 or 1 fermions in each g_i subcell by Pauli's principle. n_i is the number of particles in the i th level containing g_i subcells.

Boson arrangements = $(n_i + g_i - 1)! / \{ n_i! (g_i - 1)! \}$ ((8)) which is the number of arrangements of n_i particles and $g_i - 1$ partitions.

Taking \ln and using Stirling's approximation yields the Fermi Dirac and Bose Einstein entropies. One may consider g_i like $dx dy dz$ at the end. As shown in (5)

$$S/k = \ln(\text{number of arrangements bosons}) = \text{Sum over } i \ n_i \ln(1 + g_i/n_i) + g_i \ln(1 - n_i/g_i) \quad ((9))$$

$$S/k = \ln(\text{number of arrangements fermions}) = \text{Sum over } i \ n_i \ln(g_i/n_i - 1) - g_i \ln(1 - n_i/g_i) \quad ((10))$$

To compare this with a Shannon-like form, set $g_i = 1$ and replace n_i with $P(e_i)$. Then

$$S_{\text{boson}}/k = [1 + P(e_i)] \ln(1 + P(e_i)) - P(e_i) \ln[P(e_i)] \quad ((11))$$

$$S_{\text{fermion}}/k = [1 - P(e_i)] \ln(1 - P(e_i)) - P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i)) \quad ((12))$$

Thermodynamic Entropy

The first law of thermodynamics states that:

$$dE = TdS \text{ if external parameters are held constant} \quad ((13))$$

$$E_{\text{ave}} = \text{Sum over } i \ e_i P(e_i) \text{ so } dE_{\text{ave}} = \text{Sum over } i \ e_i dP(e_i) \quad ((14))$$

As a result, one might wish to have an entropy $S = \text{Sum over } i \ F(P(e_i))$, where F is an unknown function, which behaves in a similar manner. In (2) we showed that $F(P(e_i)) = P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i))$ is a solution, but we note here that

$$S/k = \text{Sum over } i \ (A P(e_i) + B) \ln(A P(e_i) + B) \quad ((15))$$

is a more general one because: $dS/k = \sum_i dP(e_i)A + A \sum_i dP(e_i) \ln(AP(e_i)+B)$ ((16))

This suggests that: $A \ln(AP(e_i)+B)$ should be e_i . Alternatively, one may have a sum of various Shannon-like terms with different A_j and B_j as in the fermion or boson case i.e.

$$S/k = \sum_i \sum_j (A_j P(e_i) + B_j) \ln(A_j P(e_i) + B_j) \quad ((17))$$

A key feature is that the various information pieces be linear in $P(e_i)$. For bosons and fermions this is the case. There may also be constraints on the values of A_j and B_j e.e.g from ((16)) one sees that $A_j = \pm 1$ is convenient.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that one may have more than one piece of information in a physical system yet a particle must be characterized by e_i its energy. This suggests that the two or more pieces of information must combine to form a Paltered(e_i) such that $\ln(\text{Paltered}(e_i)) = Ae_i + B$ where $A=1/T$ and $B=-u/T$, T being the temperature and u the chemical potential. This is compatible with an information theory picture of Probability = Product over i $P(e_i)^{NP(e_i)} (1-P(e_i))^{N(1-P(e_i))}$ using fermions as an example. Taking the \ln leads to a sum of Shannon-like entropies. This in turn should equal $1/\text{arrangements}$ where the number of arrangements is calculated using two pieces of information i.e. $P(e_i)$ the average number of fermions in a cell i and the information that only 1 fermion at most may occupy a subcell g_i within cell i .

Thermodynamic entropy should satisfy $dE = \sum_i e_i dP(e_i)$ so one wishes to have an entropy of the form $S/k = - \sum_i \sum_j F(A_j P(e_i) + B_j)$ where F is unknown such that $dS/k = \sum_j \sum_i G(A_j P(e_i) + B_j) dP(e_i)$ such that: $\sum_j G(A_j P(e_i) + B_j) = -e_i/T + \text{function}(T \text{ and possibly other parameters e.g. chemical potential})$. We find that $F(A_j P(e_i) + B_j) = \sum_j [A_j P(e_i) + B_j] \ln [A_j P(e_i) + B_j]$ satisfies this requirement i.e. one has a sum of Shannon-like entropies. This applies to fermions and bosons.

References

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